

Composite Materials Handbook (CMH-17): An Introduction and Overview

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- What is CMH-17?
 - Organization and Operating Structure
 - Our Members and our work
 - Goals
- What does CMH-17 Offer You?
 - Upcoming releases: Vol. 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7
 - Statistics Software
 - Education, Training, and Knowledge Sharing
- How can you get involved?

What is CMH-17?

CMH-17

COMPOSITE MATERIALS HANDBOOK

- CMH-17 stands for the Composite Material Handbook, which is supported by a Composite Material Handbook *Organization*
- The Handbook itself consists of 6 volumes published by SAE, with a 7th in work on non-metallic additive manufacturing
 - The six volumes were originally MIL-HDBK-17 (Vol 1-5) and MIL-HDBK-23 (Vol 6)
 - The FAA took over management near the turn of the century and renamed the organization in 2005
- CMH-17 operates as a volunteer organization comprised of international participants from industry, government, and academia

Key Information about CMH-17

- Aviation authorities rely on CMH-17 to supplement formal guidance:
 - Strong focus on safety, certification efficiency and workforce education
 - Rich record of lessons learned and best practices
- Although funded by the FAA, handbook content is primarily written by industry and reflects priorities of both regulators and industry members:
 - In this unique organization competitors collaborate to document common engineering, manufacturing, and maintenance guidelines and protocols for complex subjects, including those applied to ensure aircraft safety and efficient product certification, which otherwise are typically kept as proprietary practice

Our Members' Experience:

- FAA funded, chaired, and steered organization focused on safety and collaboration
- International networking with technical experts
- Collaboration across companies
- A level playing field for all membership regardless of industry segment
- Unparalleled learning opportunities with tutorials on Certification, Bonded Processes, our Statistics Software, and more

Our Organization Experiences:

- Industry consensus on content like other SDO products
- Thriving technical community of experts
- Over 20 active Working Groups and 15 active Task Groups
- Opportunities for connection, growth, and modernization based on participant feedback
- Peer-reviewed, and balloted content on industry best practices
- Biannual joint coordination meetings to deepen connections and knowledge transfer

The handbook has three goals/purposes:

1. Provide material data

- PMC, MMC, CMC, Sandwich Structure, and Non-Metallic AM
- Physical and mechanical properties
- Tied to a single material specification AND a single process specification (published elsewhere, but publicly available)

2. Describe how to generate material data

- Material and process control
- Test matrices and testing methodologies
- Statistical methods

3. Describe how to use material data

- Proven methodologies, engineering solutions, best practices, lessons learned, and case studies for the design, analysis, certification, manufacture, and field support of parts and structures made from advanced materials

- Includes significant information for aerospace applications, with benefit to other applications
- Constitutes overview of advanced composite and additive materials technology and engineering
- Volumes are continuously being updated to reflect advances in industry best practices

What's in the Handbook?

Active Items

WHAT DOES CMH-17 OFFER YOU?

Volume 3: PMC Materials Usage, Design, and Analysis

Revision H – planned release Oct 2025

CMH17

COMPOSITE MATERIALS HANDBOOK

- Volume 3 provides methodologies and lessons learned for the design, analysis, manufacture, and field support of fiber-reinforced PMC structures.
- Also provides guidance on material and process specifications and procedures for utilization of the data presented in Volume 2.
- Information is an extensive compilation of the current knowledge and experiences of the engineers and scientists from industry, government, and academia who actively apply composites to products.
- Rev H has more than doubled in content (990 Rev G pages to over 2000 pages)
 - New content on Building Block Approaches, Damage Tolerance, Structural Bonding, Design, Sustainability and Supportability, Crashworthiness, Engine and Space Applications
 - The tremendous advancement could only be achieved through collaboration and buy-in from all members

Volume 5: Ceramic Matrix Composites

Revision B – planned release Dec 2025

- Volume 5 contains CMC material system properties for which data meeting the specific requirements of the handbook are available.
- Also provides selected guidance on other technical topics related to SiC/SiC and Ox/Ox composites:
 - Material selection of constituents and external coatings
 - Material specifications, processing and quality control
 - Characterization, testing, and data reduction
 - Design and analysis
- Revision B has increased content by about 25% from Rev A
 - New content on Environmental Barrier Coatings, Engine Applications, new Data Sets, increased information on melt infiltrated (MI) SiC/SiC, Attachments, and Testing Methodologies.

Volume 2: PMC Material Properties

Revision J – planned release Spring 2026

- Volume 2 contains reviewed and approved material property data for polymer matrix composites.
 - Data is arranged in categories by reinforcement class and matrix class. Within a category, the data is in chronological order (based on when data was submitted).
 - Data is also divided by full data documentation (including public material specifications) and older partial documentation data
 - Volume 2 Annex contains data with export control restrictions
- Revision J will include new approved data sets

Volume 6: Structural Sandwich Composites

Revision A – planned release Spring 2027

- Volume 6 provides information on the design, analysis, and fabrication of composite sandwich structures
- Includes typical design values for sandwich constituent materials (core, adhesives).
- MIL-HDBK-23 information was incorporated into initial release of Volume 6.
- Revision A will include an increased emphasis on damage tolerance and damage arrestment features as primary design considerations in structural sandwich designs.
 - Volume is being reorganized and expanded from 7 into 12 chapters
 - Will document industry best practices in a range of aircraft applications from cabin interior structures to primary structural components, covering structural design and analysis, material and process controls, manufacturing implementation and maintenance practices
 - Will provide newly developed methods for assessing damage in sandwich structures for maintenance and repair.

Volume 7: Non-Metallic Additively Manufactured Materials – planned release Fall 2026

VOLUME 7

- 1 CMH-17 AM Introduction And Guidelines
- 2 Characterization Considerations
- 3 Evaluation of Feedstock
- 4 Processing and Manufacturing
- 5 Quality Control of Production Materials And Processes
- 6 Material Testing & Characterization For Submission Of Data to CMH-17
- 7 Property Testing of Additively Manufactured Materials
- 8 Statistical Methods
- 9 Evaluation of AM Parts
- 10 Element Level Testing
- 11 Design and Analysis
- 12 Maintainability And Supportability
- 13 Applications, Case Histories, and Lessons Learned
- 14 AM Property Data

Volume 7 will be a new volume covering non-metallic AM materials.

Provide knowledge necessary to efficiently design, certify, manufacture, and maintain non-metallic AM parts in aerospace applications

CMH-17 defines procedures for statistical analysis for composite testing data

Statistical methods included in CMH-17 are available in software form for purchase

Software generates A- and B-basis values and test statistics for material equivalency and acceptance testing (modified coefficient of variation (MOD CV)).

A Python based software is in development to replace the existing Excel based software

New software has finished beta testing and statistical equivalency testing

User Interface is in development

New Software and Tutorial planned for May 2026

Involvement to Influence Content Development and Learning Opportunities

- Our semi-annual meetings are an excellent networking opportunity
- In attendance are subject matter experts (SMEs) from the FAA, EASA, DoD, NASA, the worldwide aerospace industry, and academia
 - Spring meetings are in person at various sites in continental US and fall meetings are virtual
 - Meetings include “all-hands” coordination sessions, a technical forum, and working and task group meetings
 - May include mini-tutorials, FAA-sponsored research reviews, panel sessions, local industry tours
 - Offer optional 6-hour tutorials during our spring in-person meetings
- We plan to aggressively increase our training offerings, both in-person and virtually, to help explain handbook content and share best practices, particularly for the newly revised volumes.
 - Will include opportunities for Q&A with organizational SME

WE'RE WORKING ON A LOT!

New Volumes, New Revisions,
New Software, New Content,
and a New Website format, cmh17.org

PLEASE JOIN US

Getting Involved with Us – CMH-17.org

- Attend our meetings
 - Join a Working Group or Task Group
 - Follow us on LinkedIn
 - Join our mailing list
 - Attend one of our learning opportunities
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- **There is no CMH-17 membership fee for you or your company**
 - In-person meetings have modest fee to cover meeting and food costs
 - Fees are charged for tutorials

Follow us
on
LinkedIn!

Our Next Meeting – Fall 2025

- Virtual Meeting
- Tuesday-Thursday Oct 28th-30th, Nov 4th-6th
- 4 Hours a day
- info@cmh17.org

